

IDENTIFICATION OF BIOACTIVE PHYTOCHEMICALS IN THE METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *SOLIVA SESSILIS* WITH POTENTIAL APPLICATION IN DIABETIC WOUND HEALING

Mnahil Mohamed Gamal^{1*}, Mohammed Suleiman Ali Eltoum², Mai Makki²

¹Kassala University, College of Education.

²Sudan University of Science and Technology, College of Science.

*Corresponding Author: Mnahil Mohamed Gamal

Kassala University, College of Education.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152119>

How to cite this Article: Mnahil Mohamed Gamal^{1*}, Mohammed Suleiman Ali Eltoum², Mai Makki² (2026). Identification Of Bioactive Phytochemicals In The Methanolic Extract Of *Soliva Sessilis* With Potential Application In Diabetic Wound Healing. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 164-168.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/12/2025

Article Revised on 25/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

The identification of bioactive phytochemicals from medicinal plants is essential for the discovery of novel therapeutic agents, particularly for the management of chronic diseases such as diabetic wounds. The present study aimed to investigate the phytochemical composition of the methanolic leaf extract of *Soliva sessilis* using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Leaves of *S. sessilis* were extracted with 85% methanol, and resulting extract was subjected to GC-MS analysis. A total of 154 phytochemical constituents were detected, including fatty acids, esters, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and alcohols. The major compounds identified were hexadecenoic acid hexadecyl ester and hexadecanoic acid octadecyl ester (19.10%), followed by 1-hexadecanol acetate (13.04%) and hexadecanol (9.90%). Many of these compounds have been reported to possess antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities, which are crucial mechanisms involved in diabetic wound healing. FTIR analysis further confirmed the presence of key functional groups associated with these bioactive compounds. The findings provide scientific evidence supporting the traditional use of *Soliva sessilis* and highlight its potential as a natural source of bioactive agents for pharmaceutical applications in diabetic wound management.

KEYWORDS: *Soliva sessilis*, phytochemicals, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, diabetic wound healing, antimicrobial activity, antioxidant activity.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a complex metabolic disorder resulting from dysregulated glucose sensing or insulin secretion, autoimmune-mediated β -cell destruction in type 1 diabetes or insufficient compensation for peripheral insulin resistance in type 2 diabetes.^{[1][2]} It represents a major global health challenge due to its increasing prevalence and association with severe complications including delayed wound healing and chronic ulcer formation.

Chronic wounds are among the most serious and costly complications of diabetes. Diabetic patients are at the highest risk of developing chronic wounds due to the

conditions such as high glucose levels, neuropathy, poor blood circulation, and prolonged inflammation around the limbs that causes the healing to be delayed compared to normal patients.^[3] Wound healing difficulties in diabetes patients are multidirectional. The hyperglycemic condition often leads to infection, gangrene, limb amputation, and increased mortality rates. Impaired angiogenesis, prolonged inflammation, oxidative stress, reduced growth factor expression and microbial infection are key factors that contribute to delayed wound healing in diabetic patients^[4]. Moreover, open wounds are particularly prone to infection, especially by bacteria, and provide an entry point for systemic infections.^[5]

The use of plants and herbs in medicine and food offers numerous advantages. They are cost-effective, making them accessible, especially in resource-limited settings and they generally have fewer side effects compared to synthetic drugs. Herbs and spices serve as natural, non-toxic, with their sustainability, accessibility and diverse applications, plant-based remain an invaluable resource for health and wellness.^[6]

Soliva sessilis

S. Sessilis is a low-growing winter annual that germinates during the wet period in Mediterranean climate areas and grows throughout the winter when the weather is warm enough. It may also germinate in the spring and flower later that same spring acting like an annual. In British Columbia, Canada flowering occurs from March to July.^{[7][8][9]} It also known as lawnweed, common soliva, onehunga weed, field burweed, bindyi, jo jo bindi weed, bindii, or bindi-eye.^[10] *Soliva sessilis* has been used in folk medicine for the treatment of skin-related disorders, inflammation and fever.^[11]

Carpet burweed is native to South America. It has now been naturalized in Canada (British Columbia), the United States (the western and southern states), New Zealand, Australia, Taiwan and parts of Europe and Africa. The first Canadian report was in Ruckle Park on Saltspring Island in 1996.^{[10][8]}

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS)

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry is powerful analytical technique widely used for the identification and characterization of bioactive compounds in plant extracts. It provides valuable qualitative and quantitative information on complex phytochemical mixtures and supports the correlation between chemical constituents and biological activities.

To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has comprehensively reported the GC-MS profiling of the methanolic leaf extract of *Soliva sessilis*. Therefore, the present study represents the first detailed investigation of the phytochemical composition of *S. sessilis* leaves GC-MS and FTIR analysis, aiming to identify bioactive compounds that may contribute to its potential therapeutic application in diabetic wound management.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant Material Collection and Identification

Fresh leaves of *Soliva sessilis* were collected from Arkawit region, Eastern Sudan, in February 2021. The plant material was authenticated based on its morphological characteristics using standard botanical identification keys. The collected samples were thoroughly cleaned to remove soil and foreign materials prior to processing.

Preparation of Plant Extract

The leaves of *S. sessilis* were separated from other aerial parts, and air-dried at room temperature under shade to

prevent degradation of thermolabile compounds. The dried leaves were then finely ground into a uniform powder using a mechanical grinder.

Approximately 10.45 g of the powdered leaf material was macerated in 50 ml of 85% methanol in Stoppard container and kept at room temperature for 24 hours with occasional shaking to enhance extraction efficiency. The mixture was subsequently subjected to sonication at 40 °C for 60 min to ensure maximum extraction of phytochemicals.

After extraction, the solution was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure at 40 °C using rotary evaporator to obtain the crude methanolic extract.

GC-MS Analysis

Gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of the methanolic leaf extract of *Soliva sessilis* was performed at Science Way Laboratory, using a GC ISQ 7000 system equipped with a mass selective detector. Helium (99.99%) was used as carrier gas at a constant flow of 1.0 ml / min. A sample volume of 1µl was injected into system with the injector temperature set at 200 °C.

The oven temperature was initially programmed at 110°C followed by an increase at a rate of 10 °C/min to 200 °C, then 5 °C/min to 280 °C with a final isothermal hold at 280 °C for 9 minutes. The mass spectrometer was operated in electron ionization mode at 70 eV, with a mass scan range of 50 - 650 m/z.

Identification of phytochemical constituents was carried out by comparing the obtained mass spectra with those available in the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and Willey's mass spectral libraries. Compounds were tentatively identified based on spectral similarity, molecular weight, and retention time.

FTIR Analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy was employed to identify the functional groups present in the methanolic extract of *Soliva sessilis*. The FTIR spectrum was recorded in the range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The characteristic absorption peaks were analyzed to determine the major functional groups corresponding to the phytochemical constituents identified by GC-MS analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical analysis plays a crucial role in understanding the therapeutic potential of medicinal plants and supports their rational use in pharmaceutical applications. In the present study, the methanolic leaf extract of *Soliva sessilis* was analyzed using gas chromatography and mass spectroscopy to identify its bioactive constituents that may contribute to diabetic wound healing.

The GC-MS chromatographic analysis revealed a complex phytochemical profile, with a total of 154 compounds detected in the methanolic extract. The identified compounds mainly belonged to fatty acids, esters, alcohols, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, and hydrocarbons, indicating a chemically diverse extract. The GC-MS chromatogram of the methanolic extract is presented in Figure 1, showing the distribution of major and minor constituents.

Among the detected compounds, hexadecanoic acid hexadecyl ester, and hexadecanoic acid octadecyl ester were identified as the major constituents, each representing (19.10%) of the total peak area. These compounds are long-chain fatty acid esters that have been previously reported to exhibit antimicrobial, antioxidant, hypocholesterolemic and anti-inflammatory activities. Such biological properties are highly relevant to diabetic wound healing. Another prominent compound detected was 1-Hexadecanol acetate and acetic acid n-octadecyl ester (13.04%), followed by hexadecanol

(9.90%). Fatty alcohols and their esters are known for their antioxidant and antimicrobial activities, as well as their ability to enhance skin barrier function.

Several unsaturated fatty acids and their derivatives, including oleic acid, erucic acid, and octadecenoic acid esters, were also identified in moderate concentrations. Unsaturated fatty acids have been widely reported to modulate inflammatory responses, promote keratinocyte migration, and enhance angiogenesis, all of which are essential processes in wound healing.

The GC-MS analysis also revealed the presence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds, such as flavone derivatives and benzopyranone compounds. Flavonoids are well-known for their strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities. In the context of diabetic wound healing, flavonoids contribute to scavenging reactive oxygen species, inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines, and accelerating collagen synthesis and re-epithelialization.

Fig 1: GC-MS Chromatogram of *Soliva sessilis* methanolic extract.

Fig 2: MS Chromatogram of *Soliva sessilis* methanolic extract.

Table 1: Major bioactive compounds identified in the methanolic leaf extract of *Soliva sessilis* by GC-MS.

No	Compound	R.Time	Molecular Formula	Mwt g/mol	Area %	Biological Activity
1.	HEXADECANOIC ACID, HEXADECYL ESTER	85.10	C ₃₂ H ₆₄ O ₂	480	19.10	Antioxidant, antimicrobial, hypocholesterolemic, anti-inflammatory
2.	Hexadecanoic acid octadecyl ester	85.10	C ₃₄ H ₆₈ O ₂	508	19.10	Antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory
3.	1-Hexadecanol, acetate	49.29	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	284	13.04	Antioxidant, antimicrobial
4.	1-Hexadecanol	45.24	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O	242	9.90	Antioxidant
5.	HEXADECANE	35.39	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226	4.70	Antifungal, antibacterial and antioxidant
6.	Cetyl stearate	90.94	C ₃₄ H ₆₈ O ₂	508	4.14	Skin smoothing
7.	9-Octadecenoic acid (Z)-, tetradecyl ester	90.10	C ₃₂ H ₆₂ O ₂	478	3.20	Improve skin texture
8.	Oleic acid	90.10	C ₃₈ H ₇₄ O ₂	562	3.20	Improve skin hydration
9.	1H-Inden-1-one, 5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2,3-dihydro-3,3-dimethyl	46.89	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O	216	4.54	Anti-inflammatory antioxidant
10.	3,4-2H-Coumarin, 4,4,5,6,8-pentamethyl	48.32	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₆	218	7.83	Antimicrobial anticancer and anti-inflammatory
11.	Heptacosane	79.76	C ₂₇ H ₅₆	380	3.33	Antioxidant anti-inflammatory anticancer
12.	Erucic acid	55.57	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₂	338	1.04	Antibacterial

FTIR Analysis

FTIR analysis further supported the GC-MS finding by confirming the presence of key functional groups associated with the identified phytochemicals. The broad absorption band around 3418 cm⁻¹ corresponded to O-H stretching vibrations, indicating the presence of phenolic and alcoholic groups. Peaks observed in the range 2923-

2852 cm⁻¹ were attributed to aliphatic C-H stretching, consistent with fatty acids and long-chain hydrocarbons. The strong absorption at 1723 cm⁻¹ confirmed the presence of ester carbonyl (C=O) groups, while bands at 1636-1516 cm⁻¹ indicated aromatic C=C stretching vibrations, supporting the presence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds.

Fig 3: IR spectrum of *Soliva sessilis* methanolic extract.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the methanolic extract of *Soliva sessilis* is rich in bioactive compounds with documented antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities. The synergistic effects of these phytochemicals may explain the traditional use of *S. sessilis* in the treatment of skin-related disorders and support its potential application in diabetic wound management.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully characterized the phytochemical profile of the methanolic leaf extract of *Soliva sessilis* using GC-MS and FTIR analysis. The extract was found to be rich in biologically active

compounds, predominantly fatty acid esters, alcohols, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds. Several major constituents, including hexadecanoic acid esters and hexadecanol derivatives, are known for their antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, which are essential mechanisms involved in diabetic wound healing.

The findings provide scientific support for traditional medicinal use of *Soliva sessilis* in the treatment of skin-related disorders highlight its potential as a promising natural source of bioactive compounds for diabetic wound management. Further studies focusing on the isolation of individual compounds, in vitro and in vivo

biological evaluations, and formulation development are recommended to validate its therapeutic efficacy and clinical applicability.

REFERENCES

- Goboza M., Meyer S., Aboua Y.G. and Oquntibeju O.O. (2017). Diabetes mellitus: Economic and health burden, Treatment, and the therapeutic effects of Hypoxis hemerocallidea plant. *Med Technol SA*, 30(2): 39-46.
- WHO (2018). *Global Reports on Diabetes*. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- Gothia S., Muniandy K., and Zarin M. (2017). Chemical composition of Moringa oleifera ethyl acetate fraction and its biological activity in diabetic human dermal fibroblasts, *Pharmacognosy Magazine*, 13(51): 462-469.
- Patel S., Srivastava S., Singh M.R., Singh D. (2019). Mechanistic insight into diabetic wound: Pathogenesis, molecular targets and treatment strategies to pace wound healing. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 112: 108-615.
- Herman A., Herman A.P, (2023). Herbal products and their active constituents for diabetic wound healing Preclinical and clinical studies, *A systemic Review Pharmaceutics*, 15: 281.
- Abdel-Aziz M.S, Ghareeb M.A, Saad A.M Refahy L.A, Hamed A.A., (2018). Chromatographic isolation and structural elucidation of secondary metabolites from the soli inhabiting fungus *Aspergillus fumigatus* 3T-EGY. *Acta Chromatogr*, 30(4): 243-9.
- Oguntibeju O.O., (2018). Medicinal plants and their effect on diabetic wound healing. *Veterinary World*. WSWCB, 2007.
- Castro K., (2006). Weed risk assessment of Carpet burweed (*soliva sessilis*). *Canadian Food Inspection Agency*, Ottawa, 38.
- Johnson C.D., and P.H. Lovell. (1980). Germination, establishment and spread of *Soliva validiviana* (Compositae). *New Zealand Journal of Botany*, 18: 487-93.
- Alison M., (2014). Carpet Burweed (*soliva sessilis*) literature review.
- Chao Y., Yang W.L.M., Yang F., and Lee R., (2021)., *Angelica dahurica* and *Rheum officinale* facilitated diabetic wound healing by elevating vascular endothelial growth factor. *The American Journal of Chinese Medicine*, 1-19.
- Ambika A., and Nair S., (2019). Wound healing activity of plants from the Convolvulaceae family. *Advances in Wound Care*, 81: 28-37.
- Accipe L., Abadie A., Nevriere R., and Bercion S., (2023). Antioxidant activities of natural compounds from Caribbean plants to enhance diabetic wound healing. *Antioxidants* 12.
- Diab A.T., Donia K.T, and Khalil M.S.A. (2021). Characterization, antioxidant and cytotoxic effects of some Egyptian wild plant extracts. *Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 10: 13.
- Sema A., and Mehmet R.A., (2012). Kinetics of esterification of acetic acid with 1-octanol in the presence of Amberlyst 36 Applied Catalysis, A: General, 429: 79-84.